

Subject : STAMPING OF THERMOPLASTIC COMPOSITES MATERIALS
REINFORCED BY CONTINUOUS FIBRES.

D. BOUSSETA (1), M. ARTOLA (2)

Abstract : Processing industry of thermoplastic composites reinforced with long aligned fibers still requires significant development. Among these processes the thermoforming by stamping is a simple way of transformation allowing high production rate. The mechanical behaviour of the object depends on the geometry of fibers (volume and orientation). Two models are proposed in order to study the effect of each constituent in this kind of forming process : (1) net method and (2) the ideal fiber-reinforced fluid model. Models in the process of being studied are presented in conclusion.

Résumé : Les procédés de transformation des matériaux composites à matrice thermoplastique et à fibres longues nécessitent encore des développements importants. Parmi ces procédés le formage par emboutissage (ou estampage de plaques composites) est un moyen de transformation simple permettant des cadences de productions élevées. La géométrie des fibres (volume et orientation) conditionne le comportement mécanique de la pièce. Deux modèles sont proposés afin d'évaluer le rôle de chaque constituant dans ce type de mise en forme : (1) méthode du filet et (2) matériau idéal renforcé fibre (MIRF). Les modélisations en cours d'études sont présentées en conclusion.

Introduction :

The goal of this paper is to develop models and rapid computational procedures for determining the réarrangements of fibres that occurs during the stamping of thermoplastic composites reinforced by long aligned fibres from flat layups. One of the main advantage using thermoplastic polymer as matrices is their easy melting under heat and pressure.

(1) D. BOUSSETA : IMC, Université Bordeaux I

(2) M. ARTOLA : Professeur à l'Université Bordeaux I

The type of materials we consider are those in which a matrix material is reinforced by continuous fibres. We suppose that the fibres are aligned along one or more families of curves and are initially straight lines. The fibres are dense, that is that the volume concentration of fibre in the composite is quite high (> 50 per cent).

Net method :

The net method is a very simple geometric model [2] where the effect of the thermoplastic resin is neglected. Only deformation allowed for flat layup composed by two families of aligned fibres at 0° and 90° is a variation of angle between two a perpendicular fibres, the normal distance of fibres remains constant. Applied to a hemispheric shape, these constraints lead to a geometric model solved by a method of intersection of spheres. The equation of the hemispheric shape is given by

$$X^2 + Y^2 + Z^2 = R^2, \quad Z \geq 0$$

r is the normal distance between two adjacent fibres and remains constant.

θ is the angle between two fibres (initially perpendicular)

R is the radius of the hemisphere

Let $M(i,j)$ be the intersections points of the two perpendicular families of fibres initially in the plane $Z=R$. With appropriate limit condition we solve the problem :

$$\left[\begin{array}{l} M(i-1,j) \text{ and } M(i,j-1) \text{ being known, find } M(i,j) \\ M(i,j) \in S(M(i-1,j),a) \cap S(M(i,j-1),a) \cap S(O,R) \\ \text{if } Z^1(i,j) < Z^2(i,j) \text{ then } M(i,j) = M_1(i,j) \\ \text{else } M(i,j) = M_2(i,j) \end{array} \right.$$

With boundary condition :

$$M(i,0) = (0, R\sin(ix), R\cos(ix)), \quad i \geq 0$$

$$M(0,i) = (R\sin(ix), 0, R\cos(ix)), \quad i \geq 0$$

Where $x = r/R$ and $a = 2R\sin(x/2)$

Ideal fibre-reinforced fluid model :

The introduction of a family of fibres possessing a definite orientation immediately introduces a preferred direction into the material. We will therefore discuss a continuous model ([1]) of fibre-reinforced materials with no direct reference to the properties of the individual constituents. Although the properties of the materials depend on the properties of the constituents and the way they are combined, the ideal fibre-reinforced fluid model is strictly continuous model, and we make no distinction between particles of the fibre and those of the matrix.

We make the assumption that the composite is inextensible in the fibre direction and incompressible. These constraints restrict the range of possible deformation of the material. The points of a body are referred to a fixed rectangular cartesian coordinate system, and the current coordinates x_i at time t of a point on t and the coordinates X_R of the same point in a reference configuration a time $t=0$. thus.

$$x_i = x_i(X_R, t) \quad i=1,2,3$$

The unit vector field $a(X_R, t)$ describes the family of fibres at time t such that

$$a(X_R, 0) = A(X_R)$$

Where A is the fibre direction at each point in the reference configuration.

The constraints of inextensibility requires

$$a_i = \frac{\partial x_i}{\partial X_R} A_R, \quad R=1,2,3$$

$$\frac{\partial x_i}{\partial X_R} \frac{\partial x_i}{\partial X_S} A_R A_S = 1$$

The incompressibility of the material gives

$$\frac{\partial (x_1, x_2, x_3)}{\partial (x_1, x_2, x_3)} = 1$$

We apply these constraints to a hemispheric shape endowed with spherical coordinate. We discuss the analytic solution and compare to the net method

Conclusion :

These two simple models show the necessity to find more complete model taking the effect of the resin into-account. This requires the introduction of more realistic behaviour law for this material. The homogeneization theory can give a better apprehension of this behaviour. We therefore apply this theory to a viscoelastic body periodic, in two directions, made of two different viscoelastic parts in the quasi-static case. From know on we assume the fibres to be elastic and the resin to be viscous, then by properly taking the limit of the viscoelastic problem, we get the homogenized equation and coefficients of the body. The next step would be to introduce the variation of the temperature in this theory.

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